

SIMNORAT

Planning the Northern European Atlantic Ocean

Stakeholder engagement: France-Spain transboundary workshop

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Final Conference
29-30 January 2019, Brest
(France)

AGENCE FRANÇAISE
POUR LA BIODIVERSITÉ
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Stakeholder engagement: France-Spain transboundary workshop

Identification of the groups and sectors related to the use of the sea

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2nd October 2018

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Administrative, legal and management:

- **Administrative complexity** when obtaining permits for the development or implementation of a new activity.
- Lack of **bureaucratic** agility.
- Need for **transparent, simple and stable processes** over time.
- **Competence definition** of public administrations in relation to management.
- **Legal gaps** in the regulation of the uses of the marine environment.
- **Increase funding** for plans to be effective.
- Greater **financing** for the declaration of **protected areas**.

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Environmental aspects:

- The **environmental** component must be the **priority** for marine management. Better monitoring and control of water quality is needed; as well as the interactions between land and sea.
- Need to know the **environmental status** of the Bay of Biscay.
- Need to declare an **ecological corridor** Spain and France.

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Socioeconomic aspects (I)

- Lack of **knowledge** about maritime **activities** and their evolution.
- Need to analyze and share **the priorities of each activity**.
- Existence of opportunities for the development of **new activities** such as renewable energy.
- It is expected that the establishment of new activities will cause a greater **demand** for **marine space** and a **privatization of space**.
- Need to **prioritize traditional activities**, and develop new activities in less used spaces.

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Socioeconomic aspects (II)

- Search for opportunities for **coexistence of activities**.
- Need to **quantify the services** provided by marine ecosystems and the impact that activities can have on them.
- Need for **valuation of products** obtained from marine resources.
- Need to know the socio-economic **consequences of climate change**.
- Need to **overcome the idea** that economic development is not environmentally sustainable.

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General conclusions of the workshop

- **Attendees agreed** on the **importance** of this type of **workshops** to discuss the environmental and socioeconomic aspects and problems that must be addressed when developing management plans; especially when the adoption of management measures may have consequences on the other side of the border.
- **Need to learn** from the mistakes of the past, especially regarding the consultation and participation of the interested parties in cross-border areas.
- Need to develop a **network of marine protected areas (N2000)**, which is coherent and continuous between the two countries.

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- The **lack of political participation**.
- The implementation of **MSP** in **shared management** can be an interesting approach in the case of areas that share the same habitats, the same species and, in fact, the same problems with economic sectors.
- **Agreements on the governance** of the area, emphasizing that environmental protection and consistency begin with the definition of good governance.

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Merci beaucoup
Muchas gracias
Eskerrik asko

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